

CoARA Working Group

**Reforming Academic
Career Assessment
(ACA)**

RETHINKING ACADEMIC CAREER ASSESSMENT

Lessons and tools
for reform

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Lessons and tools for reform

“Evidence suggests that public, sectoral and institutional policies should ideally promote multi-dimensional career appraisal by developing consistent measures for teaching and external engagement and, to the extent possible, diversifying the set of research metrics used. Well-designed qualitative approaches will often be necessary (...).”

The above citation from [a recent report](#) of the OECD signals the need for change. Academics are evaluated at various levels and career stages, as well as in different contexts such as during recruitment and promotion. At each of these stages, assessments should be aligned with the variety of tasks, functions, and roles they fulfil. While this is well acknowledged among academics, it is far from being common practice in academic career assessment. Academics are still predominantly assessed on their research output, and often in a way that places too much emphasis on quantitative indicators. This lopsided emphasis has led to a host of undesirable effects, from stress and work dissatisfaction to questionable research practices. Reform is called for.

The CoARA Working Group ‘[Reforming Academic Career Assessment](#)’ has [surveyed nearly 200 academic organisations](#) from across Europe and beyond on their hopes and ambitions for reform. In addition, [eleven leading reform initiatives were consulted](#) on their efforts to change academic career assessment, and they have generously

[shared tools and good practices](#) that have aided them along the way.

From this wealth of data, we have drawn six important lessons and insights to help guide comprehensive and structured reform ambitions. Each of them also offers further inroads into the collected material, highlighting particular case studies, in-depth data and above all: practical tools. Although developed within the context of specific initiatives, the tools are flexible and intended to be upscaled in accordance with the needs of universities, research institutions, funders and others.

The lessons learned clearly show that change is afoot. Some lessons are confirmations of common expectations; others highlight important challenges that have yet to be resolved. In either case, they provide a snapshot of the changing field of academic career assessment. We hope they not only inspire, but also support academic institutions in making career assessment reform a reality within their organisation.

CoARA Working Group
Reforming Academic
Career Assessment
(ACA)

This document was produced by the CoARA Working Group ‘Reforming Academic Career Assessment’. The group aims to open up the dialogue on recognising and rewarding the full range of work conducted by academics in research, teaching and learning, innovation, management/leadership and service to society. In its activities the group brings together many dozens of relevant international stakeholders, including universities, learned societies and researcher associations.

1

ACADEMIC ORGANISATIONS ACROSS THE WORLD ARE MOVING TOWARDS REFORM

From Norway to Costa Rica, academic organisations across the world are looking to reform their career assessment procedures.

They signal similar concerns regarding current career evaluation practices. Academic organisations in different parts of the globe come from different starting positions, environments and cultures. Understandably, there is considerable variation in the approach and progress towards reforms. They are nonetheless all moving in a similar direction. The current global reform movement is stimulated by international initiatives, such as [DORA](#), [CoARA](#) and [CLACSO-FOLEC](#), which build upon each other's strengths. Together, we can make change a reality.

Read our case studies:

- CLACSO-FOLEC - [Declaration of principles: a new research assessment towards a socially relevant science in Latin America and the Caribbean](#)
- CoARA - [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment](#)

“There is a need for better ways to assess soft skills like pedagogy, good leadership and the ability to contribute to a good work environment.”

Learn more about the relevant data

Stage in ACA reform processes

- Reform is being considered, but no decision yet
- Reform processes are foreseen and are being planned (implementation not started yet)
- Reform is being implemented (pilot or full implementation ongoing)
- Reform processes are well established and have been fully implemented

Number of respondents: 192/192

2

REFORM IS POSSIBLE

From large universities to small research institutions, many academic organisations have initiated reforms. They have done so either on their own or through (inter)national collaboration. Successful reform hinges on a variety of factors – time, engagement, resources, academic cultures, supportive framework conditions, regulations and policies that promote and sustain change. These conditions are essential, as reforms can be either facilitated or hindered by the surrounding environment. Nonetheless, the motivation to change, one incremental step at a time, remains fundamental to reform progress. Even in countries with centrally regulated academic career assessment processes, many institutions have begun implementing reforms on their own initiative. There is no longer a first mover disadvantage, as organisations can learn from a wide range of reform experiences. By drawing on these experiences, organisations can accelerate progress and help build a supportive community of institutions undergoing similar reforms.

Get started with these practical tools:

- NOR-CAM – [career assessment matrix](#)
- DORA – [Reformscape](#)
- Recognition & Rewards – [double interview](#) on the development of career paths
- Finland – [self-evaluation tool](#) for culture of open scholarship services
- PEP-CV – [exchange platform](#) for narrative CV's

“This reform is expected to take a long time and to be a difficult path which however is 100% worth the effort (...) a critical mass of organisations needs to carry out this reform at the same time to create momentum and to achieve the goals set”

Learn more about the relevant data

Reform drivers

- The reform was initiated within the organisation
- The reform was driven by regulatory reforms at regional or national level
- The reform was inspired by best practices in other organisations or countries
- The reform was initiated together with other organisations (e.g. with similar profile, geographical proximity)
- Other

Number of respondents: 192/192

ACADEMICS ARE THE KEY TO SUCCESS

Reform is not enacted for its own sake.

Current career assessment practices negatively impact academics. Many are positive about reform, particularly early and mid-career academics. The importance of involving academic staff in reform is widely affirmed. Often, the relevance of academic career assessment reform is perceived differently depending on the career-stage of academics. Some are hesitant, unsure how reform will impact them. Although they are often consulted, academics are rarely in charge of reform efforts. Initiatives are occasionally spearheaded at a governmental or institutional management level, at other times by non-academic staff from libraries or central departments such as HR or Quality Assurance. However, to ensure the acceptance of and support for reform, academics from all disciplines and all levels of seniority need to be directly involved from the outset.

Read our case studies:

- ANECA - [Reforming research and academic careers assessment in Spain](#)
- EU Charter - [The European Charter for Researchers](#)
- YUFE4Postdocs - [YUFE4Postdocs evaluation & selection procedure](#)

Get started with these practical tools:

- ANECA - [participation platform](#) (Spanish)
- Recognition & Rewards - [toolkit for dialogue](#)
- Finland - [Report](#) on researchers' views on diversity of career assessment criteria

“The academic staff themselves developed evaluation grids that take into account various criteria to assess all the three missions, criteria that take into account the diversity of career and achievements. These grids and the related procedure have been opted for by a democratic vote of all the academic staff.”

Learn more about the relevant data

Role of academic staff in the reform process

- Academic staff (or their representatives) are actively participating in discussions on reform and in developing new processes for academic career assessment
- Academic staff (or their representatives) are consulted on the reform principles and/or steps, but are not actively involved in developing new processes for academic career assessment
- Academic staff (or their representatives) are kept informed of the reform process, but do not have an active role in the reform discussions processes or in the development of new processes for academic career assessment
- Other

Number of respondents: 192/192

4

THE SCOPE OF ACADEMIC CAREER ASSESSMENT IS EXPANDING

Research lies at the heart of academic careers. Yet academics have always engaged in a much wider range of activities beyond research. They also teach, lead, collaborate and contribute to societal needs. Until recently, the focus on academic career assessment was predominantly on research, neglecting other academic activities. There is a growing awareness that this is a limiting and biased approach that does not do justice to the manifold talents and responsibilities of academics. Instead, organisations are looking for new ways to incorporate teaching, leadership, teamwork, open science, knowledge valorisation, societal outreach, engagement with other sectors, and other activities into their assessment procedures. All of this points to a shared aim of systematically meriting academic staff for a broader scope of academic activities beyond just publications.

Learn more about the relevant data

Role of academic staff in the reform process

Read our case studies:

- Recognition & Rewards Programme – [Room for everyone’s talent in Dutch academia](#)
- NOR-CAM – [A toolbox for recognition and rewards in academic careers](#)

Get started with these practical tools:

- Recognition & Rewards – [five good practices](#) in developing career paths
- NOR-CAM – [career assessment matrix](#)
- Finland – [researcher’s curriculum vitae](#)
- European Commission – the European competence framework for researchers ([ResearchComp](#))
- ANECA – [narrative CV template](#) (Spanish)
- DORA – [guide to the narrative CV](#)

“Undertaking a reform of the evaluation system is intended to have a number of positive effects (...) the fact of evaluating research with criteria that are not solely quantitative and do not give excessive priority to the publication of papers, aims to encourage greater recognition of other tasks such as transfer, teaching, commitment with outreach activities, better working environment, etc.”

5

BIBLIOMETRICS TELL A STORY, BUT NOT THE WHOLE STORY

Although there are considerable differences between fields, publication-based metrics have formed the gold standard for assessing academic careers in many disciplines.

Increasingly, academic organisations are realising that they only give limited perspective on academic achievements. Not only do bibliometric data offer little insight into activities such as teaching or management, they also tell a one-sided and often biased story about research itself. A new approach to academic career assessment is called for, in which qualitative assessment criteria and methods are supported by responsible use of bibliometric and complementary quantitative data. This in turn will require careful consideration and documentation, as well as negotiation about relevant assessment dimensions and expectations.

Read our case studies:

- DORA – [the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment](#)

Get started with these practical tools:

- CoARA – [practical tools and options](#)
- YUFE4Postdocs – [structured CV template](#)
- Finland – [recommendation on responsible use of metrics](#)
- DORA – [unintended cognitive and systems biases](#)

“There will be a combination of qualitative assessment and responsible use of metrics. The most difficult part is to change the culture of considering the JIF as a quality proxy for the research output (...) the peer-reviewers may implicitly rely on it to assess the quality of research (...) This needs a change in mentality and culture which will take long to effectuate.”

Learn more about the relevant data

Focus of ACA after the reform

- Purely qualitative assessment
- Responsible use of metrics
- Balanced use of qualitative assessment and metrics
- Not defined yet
- I do not know/difficult to say

Number of respondents: 192/192

REFORM REQUIRES AN OPEN CONVERSATION ON THE NATURE OF QUALITY AND EXCELLENCE

Reform brings with it a period of uncertainty. New assessment criteria are being formulated, new procedures developed.

Different parties within a reforming organisation hold diverging views on what ‘excellent research’ or ‘outstanding teaching’ actually means. For reform to succeed, ideals of academic excellence and related assessment criteria should be critically discussed. Not only within the context of academic organisations and their missions, but also more broadly within disciplines and research cultures. What is needed is an inclusive conversation on what excellence entails, and how it can best be evaluated and measured.

Read our case studies:

- Finland - [Recommendation for the responsible evaluation of a researcher in Finland](#)
- OR4 - [Open and Responsible Researcher Reward and Recognition](#)
- UKRI - [UKRI People and Teams Action Plan](#)

Get started with these practical tools:

- Finland - [self-evaluation tool](#) for culture of open scholarship services and [monitoring model for open science and research](#)
- OR4 - [self-assessment tool and maturity framework](#)

“We need transparency in promotion procedures and decisions. There is no clear definition of quality for the process, giving the promotion procedure the impression of a black box.”

“There is a high diversity of scientific disciplines with impact meaning different things in different areas.”

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